

A NOVEL CONCEPT FOR CONFORMAL LOAD-BEARING ANTENNA STRUCTURES USING DISSIMILAR COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The Conformal Load-bearing Antenna Structure (CLAS) is a multifunctional aircraft structure that involves embedding electromagnetic radiators within a load bearing structure. Current design methods for CLAS contains slots in load-bearing structures. The slots inevitably create stress concentrations that reduce the overall stiffness and strength of the structure.

This paper presents a comparative investigation of a number of alternative structural concepts to maximize the strength of CLAS. These concepts enable the creation of a radar transparent window in the carbon fibre composite structure.

2 Experiment

Joints were manufactured using two different systems of prepreg with autoclave cure (120^oC, 1 hr). The Carbon/Epoxy and Glass/Epoxy composite used were T300/VTM264 and E-glass/MTM57 respectively, both provided by Advanced Composites Group, Australia.

Quasi-isotropic laminates, stacking sequence [45/0/-45/90]_{2s} made of carbon fibre and glass fibre composites were joined together using four different concepts, as shown in Figure 1: (a) step-ply joints, (b) co-cured scarf joints, (c) overlap-ply joint and (d) hybrid step-ply and overlap-ply joints.

Because the GRFP plies employed in this investigation are thicker than the CFRP plies, there is a noticeable thickness change in all joint geometries, with the changes in ply angles being the greatest in the overlapped-ply joint which causes a bulge in the joint area. Figure 2 show the micrographs of two joints made using the step-ply and overlap-ply techniques.

Joints are loaded under tension until failure to characterize the failure mechanisms and the strengths of four joint types.

Figure 1: Joint configurations: (1) stepped-ply, (2) co-cured scarf, (3) overlapped-ply, and (4) hybrid stepped-ply and overlapped-ply.

Figure 2 Micrographs of (a) step-ply joint and (b) overlap-ply joint.

3 Results

3.1 Failure modes

Failures of the different type of joints are found to be predominately delamination followed by ply rupture. Figure 3 show the images of fractured samples.

(a) Step-ply joint

(b) Overlap-ply joint

Figure 3 Failure modes single stepped-ply joint

3.2 Strength comparison

A comparison of the strengths of the four different joints with the strength of the quasi-isotropic glass laminate is presented in Figure 4. The results show that the hybrid step-ply and overlap-ply, in which only the main load-carrying zero degree plies are overlapped, gives a strength very close to the strength of the glass-fibre reinforced composites.

4 Conclusions

This study examined the load-carrying capacities and the failure mechanisms of four types of hybrid composites joints. The results show that the step-ply joints are able to achieve 50% of the un-notched strength of GFRP. By comparison, hybrid step-ply and overlap-ply joints are capable of matching the strength of the GRFP.

References

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